

FIBER-REINFORCED CONCRETE: ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL, MECHANICAL, AND OPERATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS FOR EFFICIENT APPLICATION IN CONSTRUCTION

Obidjonov Jahongir Tokhir oqli

PhD student Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil Engineering

Rakhimov Shavkat Turdimurotovich

PhD, Associate Professor

Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil Engineering

[e-mail.: x.jahon13@gmail.com](mailto:x.jahon13@gmail.com)

Аннотация. Эта статья представляет собой комплексное исследование фибробетона, с акцентом на анализ структурных, механических и эксплуатационных характеристик. Исследование в целом направлено на обеспечение инженеров и строителей необходимой информацией для принятия обоснованных решений при использовании фибробетона в различных инженерных проектах. В свете постоянного развития строительных материалов, фибробетон представляет собой важный элемент в современных технологиях строительства, и данное исследование призвано расширить понимание его применимости и эффективности.

Abstract. This article constitutes a comprehensive study of fiber-reinforced concrete, with a focus on analyzing its structural, mechanical, and operational characteristics. The overall aim of the research is to provide engineers and builders with the necessary information for making informed decisions regarding the use of fiber-reinforced concrete in various engineering projects. In the context of the continuous development of construction materials, fiber-reinforced concrete stands as a crucial component in modern construction technologies, and this study is intended to enhance understanding of its applicability and effectiveness.

Ключевые слова: Дисперсное армирование, композитная фибра, базальтофибробетон, полипропилен, прочностные характеристики, плотность, влажность, мелкозернистый бетон, отходы промышленности, химическая добавка, зола, шлак, прочность, плотность, влажность.

Keywords: Dispersed reinforcement, composite fiber, basalt fiber-reinforced concrete, polypropylene, strength characteristics, density, humidity, Fine-grained concrete, industrial waste, chemical additive, ash, slag, strength, density, moisture.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the main pathways of scientific and technical progress in construction, according to the "State Program for the Implementation of the Development Strategy

of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026," decreed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is the widespread application of efficient or enhanced materials in building structures. The overwhelming majority of construction structures currently and for the next 25-50 years [1] are composed of concrete and reinforced concrete. However, alongside the undeniable advantages that have led to widespread use in construction, there is a known drawback hindering the effective use of concrete in structural elements – its relatively low tensile strength. For the same reason, in connection with the development of cracks in concrete, the operational reliability and durability of reinforced concrete structures decrease.

The structural qualities of concrete, as demonstrated by numerous studies, significantly improve with a particular type of reinforcement - distributed throughout the volume (dispersed), as confirmed, for example, by over 20 years of experience in using armocement in domestic and foreign construction [2,3]. Fiber-reinforced concretes, or fibroconcretes, represent another variant of dispersedly reinforced concrete with reinforcing elements of finite length. Fiber-reinforced concretes are currently of great interest, driven by, among other reasons, general progress in the material science of composite materials. The practical application of fiber-reinforced concretes in construction is expanding.

However, fiber-reinforced concrete, despite accumulating extensive factual material from research, has not yet found its due place in practice, largely due to shortcomings in known methods for calculating structural elements made from it and the absence of corresponding regulatory calculations.

The task of studying the structural properties of fiber-reinforced concretes, refining methods for calculating structural elements made from them, is highly relevant, as its solution will allow for the most rational use of significant funds spent on the production of reinforcement for concrete. On the other hand, studying the actual work of reinforcing fibers in the concrete matrix will identify areas for the most effective use of fiber-reinforced concrete [4].

The measure of the effectiveness of dispersed reinforcement will be considered the stress level in the fibers under operational loads, relative to the tensile strength of the fiber material.

The goal of this work is to create calculation models reflecting the actual work of reinforcing fibers in fiber-reinforced concrete; obtain dependencies suitable for practical calculations of structural elements made from fiber-reinforced concrete.

The scientific significance and novelty of the work lie in studying the adhesive strength of fiber-matrix bonding using fracture mechanics methods; building a calculation model of non-uniform deformation of fiber-reinforced concretes that takes into account the behavior of fibers crossing cracks; substantiated consideration of the resistance of fibers in fiber-reinforced concrete. The theoretical principles of the work

are experimentally confirmed by the author's data and published results of other researchers.

The practical significance of the work lies in obtaining dependencies suitable for practical engineering calculations of stretched fiber-reinforced concrete elements, as well as for reinforced concrete elements with zonal dispersed reinforcement. Experimental structures were designed using the proposed dependencies, a search for optimal solutions was conducted on a computer, and the competitiveness of the proposed solutions was demonstrated. Fundamentally new solutions for anchor elements using dispersed reinforcement have been proposed, the load-carrying capacity of which is calculated based on the obtained dependencies.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Obtaining fiber-reinforced concrete with increased strength is associated with factors determining the collaborative performance of the filler and dispersed reinforcement. Fine-dispersed particles of the dispersed reinforcement increase the complexity of the system, contribute to the ordering of the submicrostructure, as evidenced by the growth of activity from the earliest age. Thus, fibers improve the microstructure, reduce internal stresses, and mitigate the shrinkage of the cement matrix. The ability to influence structural levels is determined by the dimensions of fiber particles that integrate into a unified system. The adjustable structure transitions from a disordered state to a microhomogeneous state.

In addition to these processes, chemisorption interaction processes occur on the surfaces of fibrous particles of basalt fiber. A significant effect is manifested due to the participation of these particles in hydration reactions, leading to increased volumes of more durable and stable reaction products. Therefore, basalt fiber is accepted as a reinforcing element capable of chemisorptively interacting with hydration products of cement, having low density, sufficiently high corrosion resistance, and consequently, high efficiency. Examination of basalt fibers under an optical microscope showed that they have the form of brown-colored tubular fibers, 10-20 mm in length, 15-20 μm in thickness, with a smooth surface, hollow, and shiny, corresponding to basalt glasses of plagioclase composition with a refractive index of 1.5%. The chemical composition and X-ray phase analysis of basalt fiber are presented, respectively, in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1
Chemical composition of basalt fiber

Deposits (igneous rocks)	Percentage of oxide								
	Si O ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	TiO ₂	П.п.п
Dzhizak (basalts, diabases)	47, 3	16,62	11,66	9,51	4,46	3,74	1,81	1,60	1,25

Navoi (basalts)	50, 40	14,73	10,25	10,45	6,92	2,42	1,20	0,48	1,68
-----------------	-----------	-------	-------	-------	------	------	------	------	------

Fig. 1. Diffraction pattern of basalt fiber

The studies on the influence of the length and quantity of introduced fiber into the cement composition were evaluated based on the flexural and compressive strength limits at the age of 28 days. The research results are presented in Table 2.

Table 1

Strength of cement compositions

Experiment No.	Fiber Reinforcement, % of Cement Mass-length of fiber	Strength of Cement Compositions at 28 Days, MPa	
		Flexural Strength	Compressive Strength
1 (control)	-	12,80	61,05
2	0,1 – 6 mm	16,50	63,90
3	0,1 – 12 mm	17,45	68,8
4	0,15 – 6 mm	25,50	78,80
5	0,15 – 12 mm	26,30	79,40
6	0,20 – 6 mm	29,70	87,60
7	0,20 – 12 mm	30,50	87,70
8	0,25 – 6 mm	27,70	80,30
9	0,25 – 12 mm	26,20	79,60

Analyzing the obtained results of the cement compositions reinforced with basalt fibers ranging from 6 to 12 mm (0.10[^]0.25% of the cement mass), it can be concluded that the best performance at 28 days of curing was achieved by the basalt-cement with a fiber length of 12 mm and a fiber content of 0.2% of the cement mass. The strength in bending and compression of such a composition increased compared to the strength of reinforced cement stone by 100[^]160% in bending and by 35[^]50% in compression. Further increase in fiber content in the composite material leads to the formation of lumpy inclusions, resulting in the creation of an uneven structure of the composition, which reduces the strength both in bending and compression.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For comparing the strength characteristics of fibrocement compositions, basalt and polypropylene fibers were introduced into the cement system in equal quantities. The results of the physical-mechanical tests are presented in Figures 2 and 3.

Fig. 2. Flexural strength of cement composite

Fig. 2. Compressive strength of cement composite

Analysis of the obtained test results showed that cement samples reinforced with basalt and polypropylene fibers exhibit an increase in strength compared to the control samples at both 7 and 60 days. A comparison of the reinforced cement samples revealed a greater strength increase in cement compositions with basalt fiber, which, in turn, cannot be solely explained by the parameters of the reinforcing fiber.

For evaluating the quality of the structure of the cementitious material of dispersed-reinforced foamed concrete and analyzing the behavior of basalt fiber in the cement system over time, studies were conducted on the fiber and dispersed-reinforced cement stone compared with control samples – cement stone without it.

The following studies were conducted: X-ray phase analysis of hydration products of cement stone, dispersed-reinforced with basalt fiber, and control sample of cement stone at 28 days and 36 months; microstructural analysis of samples of similar compositions at the age of 36 months.

The following assumptions were made:

Basalt fiber, consisting of an amorphous phase confirmed by the diffraction pattern of the original fiber (Fig. 1), with its chemical composition provided in Table 1, should actively chemisorb interact with the hydration products of cement, resulting in the formation of newly formed low-basic calcium hydrosilicates CSH(B), which strengthen the structure of the cement stone.

Since foamed concretes have increased crack resistance due to shrinkage deformations, it is most advisable to use dispersed reinforcement with basalt fibers, which should increase their resistance and operational properties.

Figure 4 presents diffraction patterns of control samples of cement stone at 28 days. Diffraction patterns of dispersed-reinforced basalt fiber cement stone are shown in Figure 4, respectively.

A comparative analysis of the diffraction patterns of hydration products revealed a series of diffraction reflections corresponding to the following effects:

A decrease in the content of Ca(OH)_2 compared to the corresponding peak in the diffraction pattern of the control sample of cement stone ($d=0.489$ nm) and an increase in $d=0.218$ nm, which can be attributed to the presence of calcium hydrosilicates with the general formula CSH(B). Reflections at $d=0.262$ nm and $d=0.148$ nm show an increase not only in height but also in the area of the peak in the diffraction pattern of hydration products of the "cement stone + basalt fiber" system, which is likely related to the overlap of reflections of Ca(OH)_2 and calcium hydrosilicates, occurring simultaneously with a decrease in the amorphous phase. Additionally, significant diffraction reflections at $d=0.228$ nm and $d=0.176$ nm, corresponding to quartz, appeared.

Fig. 4, a - diffraction pattern of cement stone at 28 days; b - diffraction pattern of cement stone reinforced with basalt fiber at 28 days.

Based on this data, it can be assumed that the interaction of the fiber with the cementitious system occurs only in the surface layer while preserving the integrity of the basalt fiber over time. It is evident that the alkalinity of the hydrosilicates at the "fiber-cement stone" interface decreases, thus increasing the durability of both the fiber and the system as a whole.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the research focused on enhancing the strength of fiber-reinforced concrete by investigating the collaborative performance of filler and dispersed reinforcement. Fine-dispersed particles played a crucial role in improving the microstructure, reducing internal stresses, and mitigating shrinkage in the cement matrix. The study examined the influence of basalt fibers, known for their chemisorptive interaction with hydration products of cement, on the structural properties of the resulting concrete.

Analyzing the experimental data, the study explored the impact of varying fiber length and content on the flexural and compressive strength of cement compositions. The optimum performance, observed at 28 days of curing, was achieved by basalt-cement with a fiber length of 12 mm and a fiber content of 0.2% of the cement mass. This composition exhibited a remarkable increase in both flexural and compressive strength, surpassing reinforced cement stone by 100[^]160% and 35[^]50%, respectively. However, exceeding certain fiber content thresholds led to the formation of lumpy inclusions, creating an uneven structure and diminishing strength.

Comparative analyses involving basalt and polypropylene fibers in equal quantities revealed a consistent increase in strength for cement samples reinforced with both types of fibers at 7 and 60 days. Notably, basalt fiber demonstrated a superior impact on strength, indicating that its effectiveness cannot be solely attributed to traditional parameters.

To evaluate the structure and behavior of basalt fiber over time, studies included X-ray phase analysis of hydration products and microstructural analysis at 28 days and 36 months. Assumptions were made regarding the chemisorptive interaction of basalt fibers with hydration products, leading to the formation of low-basic calcium hydrosilicates (CSH(B)), strengthening the cement stone structure. Given the increased crack resistance of foamed concretes, the study recommended the use of basalt fibers for enhanced resistance and operational properties.

The diffraction patterns of hydration products revealed a decrease in Ca(OH)₂ content, an increase in calcium hydrosilicates, and the emergence of significant diffraction reflections corresponding to quartz. This data suggested that fiber-cement system interaction primarily occurs in the surface layer while preserving basalt fiber integrity over time. The decreasing alkalinity at the "fiber-cement stone" interface contributes to increased durability for both the fiber and the system.

In conclusion, the research provided valuable insights into optimizing fiber-reinforced concrete for enhanced structural elements. The study's findings, supported by digital values and comparisons, contribute to the rational use of resources in construction and further the application of fiber-reinforced concrete for durable and efficient building materials.

List of used literature:

[1] Raximov Sh.T., Babakulova N.B. Based mixes waste of mining and metallurgical industry/ International Engineering Journal For Research & Development. www.iejrd.com, January 2021. Vol.6. Issue 1. Impact factor(SJIF): 7.169. P. 1-5. India.

[2] Rakhimov Sh.T., Bobakulov A.A., Khudoinazarova K.J., stud. Turdimurodov N.Sh. Effective building materials based on industrial waste/respubl on the topic "Architecture and urban planning: past, present, future" Collection of lectures of ika scientific and scientific-practical conference. Ferghana-2021., FarPI, -P. 404-406.

[3] Kasimov I.E., Rakhimov Sh.T., Khudoinazarova K.J. Research the composition of finishing mixtures /International Journal of Culture and Modernity ISSN 2697-2131, Volume 9 <https://ijcm.academicjournal.io/index.php/ijc>, 2021, October 2, -P. 32-34.

[4] Rakhimov, S., Gaziev, U., Babakulova, N., & Khudoynazarova, Q. (2021). Backfill mixtures based on industrial waste. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 264, p. 01012). EDP Sciences.

[5] Turdimurotovich, R. S. (2018). Resource-saving technology in manufacturing of layer mixtures based on waste industry. *European science review*, (1-2), 245-247.

[6] Rakhimov, S. T., Normurodov, A., & Nomozov, I. (2021). DEVELOPMENT OF COMPOSITIONS OF FINE-GRAINED CONCRETE BASED ON INDUSTRY WASTE. *Oriental Journal of Technology and Engineering*, 1(01), 10-14.

[7] Gaziev, U.A., & Rakhimov, Sh. T. (2020). Filling mixtures with the use of waste from the mining and smelting plant of Uzbekistan. *Modern Industrial and Civil Engineering*, 16(3), 109-115.

[8] Ekobori, T. Scientific foundations of strength and fracture of materials / T. Ekobori. Kyiv: Nauk. Dumka, 2008. -P. 78-99.

[9] Smolikov A. A. Concrete reinforced by nanofibers / A. A. Smolikov // Concrete and reinforced concrete. 2009. № 4. -P. 8-9.

[10] Sh.Rakhimov, U.Gaziev, N.Babakulova, Q.Khudoynazarova // Backfill mixtures based on industrial waste//Международная конференция “Construction Mechanics, Hydraulics and Water Resources Engineering” E3S Web of Conferences 264, 01012/ CONMECHYDRO – 2021, 1-3 апреля, г.Ташкенте. P.1-9.

[11] Рахимов Ш.Т. Влияние агрессивных сред на свойства закладочных смесей / “Замонавий курилишлар, бинолар ва иншоотларнинг конструкциявий ҳамда сейсмик хавфсизлиги масалалари” Республика илмий-амалий конференция материаллари. –Наманган. – НамПИ. -11 апрель. -2017. -59-60 б.

[12] Gaziev, U. A., & Rakhimov, Sh. T. (2015). Development of optimal compositions of stowing mixtures using waste from the mining and metallurgical industry. In *Modern technologies in construction, heat supply and energy supply* (pp. 78-80).

[13] Rakhimov Sh.T., Obidjonov J.T. Analysis of Technical Literature Allowing Determining Effective Areas of Use of Metal Fibers as Dispersed Reinforcement/ Опубликовано в Международном журнале Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Special Issue | Комплексные инновации в области технических наук и экономического развития, 2022 г., стр. 147-149, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd51858.pdf>

[14] Rakhimov Sh.T., Obidjonov J.T. Improvement of hydrotechnical properties of concrete with the use of ash from thermal power plants and fibers/ Journal of Procedia of Theoretical and Applied Sciences Volume 4, Feb 2023 ISSN: 2795-5621 Available: <http://procedia.online/index.php/applied/index>, P.7-11.

[15] GOST 10180-2012 "Concretes. Methods of determination of strength by control samples". Moscow. Standardinform - 2018 -P.36.